

Methyl orange dye immobilized multi-walled carbon nanotube modified electrode for a selective electrochemical sensing of ascorbic acid at low potential

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Abstract : A methyl orange (MO) dye electrochemically immobilized multi-walled carbon nanotubes modified glassy carbon electrode, designated as GCE/MWCNT@MO, has been prepared and used for selective determination of ascorbic acid (AA, vitamin C) at a very low potential (-140 mV vs Ag/AgCl) by voltammetric techniques in pH 7 phosphate buffer solution. Physicochemical characterization of the modified electrode by FTIR and Raman revealed presence of surface confined MO on MWCNT matrices. Electrochemical investigations like loading, scan rate, pH and concentration effects were studied. Amperometric *i-t* response showed a AA linear calibration range 25–600 μM with a correlation coefficient of 0.9985 and detection limit 150 nM. The present system doesn't show any interference with nitrite, cysteine, glucose and dopamine. Some pharmaceutical formulations were tested with the present system with appreciable recovery values.

Keywords : Multi-walled carbon nanotubes, methyl orange, ascorbic acid electrocatalysis, pharmaceutical formulations samples.

Introduction

Ascorbic acid (AA, dehydroascorbic acid and vitamin C), is a well know radical scavenger and anti-oxidant that plays a vital role in biological system. Its deficiency leads to the diseases like scurvy and prevents many infections for humans. Daily recommended intake of AA is about 70–90 mg for adults¹. Because of its biological importance, the determination of AA level in pharmaceutical and food products attained considerable interest during quality control stages. Several methods were reported for the determination of AA : spectroscopic, chromatographic and electrochemical techniques². Among them, electrochemical detection method seems to be simple, efficient, highly sensitive and selective without any separation procedures. However, direct oxidation of AA on bare electrode occurs at very high over potential due to electron fouling. In addition, some of the biological molecules like dopamine and uric acid undergo oxidation at the same potential as AA. Hence, development of electrochemical sensors for the selective AA detection is of prime importance in biological applications.

Several chemically modified electrodes (CMEs) based on redox mediators like organic dyes such as acriflavine³, methylene blue⁴, direct blue 71⁵, bromocresol blue 6⁸, nile blue⁷, acid yellow 9⁸, congo red⁹ and naphthol green B¹⁰ were reported for the oxidation of AA in the literature. However, efficiency of the electron transfer process as well as reduction of over oxidation potential was directly linked to the nature of the matrices in which the electroactive species were immobilized. For instance, naphthol green B dye-doped-poly pyrrole modified electrode showed significantly reduced AA oxidation over potential for about 320 mV vs Ag/AgCl with bare electrode (580 mV vs Ag/AgCl) in pH 4 oxalate buffer solutions¹⁰. First time in this work, we introduce methyl orange, MO (an azo dye) immobilized multi-walled carbon nanotubes modified electrode (named as GCE/MWCNT@MO) for the oxidation of AA at a very low potential (-140 mV vs Ag/AgCl) in the physiological solution.

MO, a halo chromic compound with an anionic terminal was commonly used in volumetric titrations as pH indicator due to the sharpen end point at mid-strength acids. The oxidation of amino terminated functional in MO will promote the electron and proton transfer reactions. Previously, azo dye compounds such as direct blue

71⁵, acid yellow 9⁸ and congo red⁹ modified electrodes were reported for the oxidation of AA. Here in, GCE/MWCNT@MO, prepared by simple chemical method, for highly sensitive detection of AA in physiological solution. The present system exhibits several advantages such as efficient electrocatalysis, high selectivity, sensitivity and low detection limit at a negative potential over the conventional chemically modified electrodes¹¹. In further, analytical performance of this system was studied by determining the AA content in pharmaceutical drug samples.

Experimental

MO, MWCNTs (>90% carbon basis, outer diameter : 10–15 nm; inner diameter : 2–6 nm; length 0.1–10 μm), SWCNT were purchased from Sigma Aldrich. Other chemicals used were all of ACS-certified reagent grade and used without further purification. AA containing pharmaceutical tablets (Celin 500 mg, #1 and Limcee 400 mg, #2) was purchased from local medical shop nearby VIT. Aqueous solutions were prepared using deionized and alkaline potassium permanganate distilled (DD) water. The supporting electrolyte pH 7 phosphate buffer solution (PBS) of ionic strength, $I = 0.1 \text{ mol L}^{-1}$ was used throughout this work.

Voltammetric measurements were all carried out with CHI Model 440B electrochemical workstation (USA). The three-electrode system consists of glassy carbon electrode (GCE) and its CMEs as a working electrode (0.0707 cm^2), Ag/AgCl as a reference and platinum wire as the auxiliary electrodes. Raman spectroscopic analysis was performed by using AZILTRON, PRO 532, (USA) with 532 nm laser excitation. For FTIR analysis JASCO 4100 Spectrophotometer was used by the KBr method.

Surface of the GCE was cleaned both mechanically and electrochemically by polishing with 0.5 micron alumina powder, washing with DD water followed by performing CV for 10 cycles in the potential window -0.2 to 1 V vs Ag/AgCl at $\nu = 50 \text{ mV s}^{-1}$ in pH 7 PBS. The GCE/MWCNT modified electrode was prepared by drop coating of $5 \mu\text{L}$ (1 mg MWCNT suspended $500 \mu\text{L}$ ethanol, 10 min sonicated stock solution) on cleaned GCE surface and drying the electrode in air for $3 \pm 1 \text{ min}$ at room temperature ($25 \pm 2 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$). Further, $5 \mu\text{L}$ MO solution (1 mg MO/ $500 \mu\text{L}$ ethanol) was drop casted on a

GCE/MWCNT surface followed by drying the electrode in air at room temperature for $3 \pm 1 \text{ min}$. Overall preparation time for the present electrode was $14 \pm 1 \text{ min}$. The AA containing real samples (#1, #2) were weighed accurately and dissolved in 10 ml PBS then $25 \mu\text{L}$ was subjected to real sample analysis.

Results and discussion

Physicochemical characterizations of MWCNT@MO by FTIR and Raman were displayed in Fig. 1. In FTIR analysis, the characteristic peaks of MO viz. $\nu(\text{S}=\text{O})$ at 1038.6 cm^{-1} , $\nu(\text{C}-\text{N})$ at 1363.6 cm^{-1} and $\nu(\text{N}=\text{N})$ at 1605.7 cm^{-1} were observed¹². The Raman spectra showed the specific peaks namely D band (disordered sp^3 carbon sites) and G band (ordered hexagonal sp^2 carbon structures) at ~ 1330 and $\sim 1570 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively. The intensification of D and G bands, i.e. $I_{\text{D}}/I_{\text{G}}$ can be taken as a measure for the degree of graphitic disorderness¹³. The increase in $I_{\text{D}}/I_{\text{G}}$ ratio values from 0.55 (GCE/MWCNT) to 0.61 (GCE/MWCNT@MO) indicate increase in the sp^3 carbon sites, presumably the MO's nitrogen and oxygen groups, on MWCNT. Thus, the overall observation confirms the presence of MO and its unknown derivatives on the MWCNT@MO.

Fig. 2A shows the continuous CV response ($n=10$) of $5 \mu\text{L}$ ethanolic MO drop casted on GCE/MWCNT in a potential window -0.4 to 0.4 V vs Ag/AgCl at the scan rate (ν) of 50 mV s^{-1} in 0.1 M pH 7 PBS. Two defined redox peaks were observed at the apparent potential ($E_{1/2}$) of $-70 \pm 6 \text{ mV}$ (A1/C1) and $162 \pm 4 \text{ mV}$ (A2/C2) vs Ag/AgCl. The surface excess values of A1/C1 and A2/C2 are 0.63 and 0.21 nmol/cm^2 , respectively. Exact detail for the redox behaviors is unknown for us now. Prior to the experiment, unmodified GCE was also tested by drop casting $5 \mu\text{L}$ ethanolic MO solution. Interestingly no stable redox peak was observed (data not enclosed). The modified electrode was subjected to scan rate effect. A linear increase in the anodic peak current (i_{pa}) response against scan rate was observed. Double logarithmic plot of i_{pa} vs ν yield a slope value of 0.6. The value obtained is between the standard slope values of 0.5 and 1 respectively for the diffusion and adsorption controlled electron transfer reactions. Mixed adsorption-diffusion controlled mechanism is proposed as a possible electron-transfer reaction in the modified electrode.

Fig. 1. (A) Typical FTIR spectra of MO, MWCNT and MWCNT@MO modified system by KBr pellet method. (B) Raman spectra of MWCNT and MWCNT@MO modified system.

Fig. 2. Typical CV response of (A) MO on MWCNT in pH 7 PBS and (B) catalytic behavior of GCE/MWCNT@MO and MWCNT system in 5 mM AA at ν of 10 mV s⁻¹ in pH 7 PBS, Amperometric responses of (C) GCE/MWCNT@MO with increasing concentration of AA and (D) interference studies at $E_{app} = -0.14$ V vs Ag/AgCl in pH 7 PBS.

Different CNTs such as SWCNT, acid treated p-MWCNT and f-MWCNT were also subjected to electro-assisted MO immobilization. Among these CNTs, i-MWCNT showed efficient loading of MO with respect to I' values (A1/C1) as below : SWCNT (0.02 nmol/cm²), p-MWCNT (0.03 nmol/cm²), f-MWCNT (0.12 nmol/cm²) and i-MWCNT (0.63 nmol/cm²). Presence of impurities such as carbonaceous graphite and nano metal oxides (NiO, Co₂O₃ and Fe₂O₃) in the pristine MWCNT¹⁴ may have some positive interaction with the MO and hence resulted to increased loading. In further, effect of solution pH on the redox behavior of GCE/MWCNT@MO was investigated. The corresponding CV responses showed systematic variation in the peak potentials against pH solution (data not shown). Plot of E_{pa} vs pH solution was linear with a slope value of -37 mV/pH; which attributes pH dependent Nerstian type electron-transfer mechanism.

Fig. 2B displays comparative electrochemical response of GCE/MWCNT@MO and GCE/MWCNT for 5 mM AA oxidation reaction in pH 7 PBS. The oxidation of AA on unmodified electrode occurred at 175 ± 5 mV vs Ag/AgCl; while on GCE/MWCNT@MO occurred at -140 ± 10 mV vs Ag/AgCl, where the A1/C1 redox peak exist. This is the first observation for the oxidation of AA at a very low potential. Fig. 2C is the comparative amperometric $i-t$ responses of GCE, GCE/MWCNT and GCE/MWCNT@MO for the continuous spikes of 25 μM AA at an applied potential (E_{app}) of -0.14 V vs Ag/AgCl in pH 7 PBS. The calibration plot is linear from 25 μM to 600 μM with the current sensitivity and regression coefficient values of 0.0368 μA/μM and 0.9983 respectively, which are superior than other conventional electrodes¹¹. Calculated relative standard deviation (RSD) and limit of detection values (S/N ratio = 3) are 0.63% and 150 nM.

In further, selectivity of the GCE/MWCNT@MO system was also studied. The system showed tolerable response with cysteine (CySH), dopamine (DA), uric acid (UA), and nitrate (NO_3^-) (Fig. 2D) unlike to the existing CMEs^{3,8}. Further, the analytical performance of the system was examined by subjecting to real sample analysis (pharmaceutical tablets) by standard addition approach. The obtained analytical values were very closer to the labeled values with the recovery values of $100 \pm 5\%$.

Table 1. Determination of AA in pharmaceutical samples

Samples	Detected (μM)	Spiked (μM)	Detected after spiked (μM)	Recovery (%)
Celin 500 mg, #1	10.22	25	25.9	101.2
		50	50.2	
		75	74.6	
Limcee 400 mg, #2	7.88	25	24.9	99.9
		50	49.9	
		75	75.2	

Conclusion

MO immobilized pristine-MWCNT modified glassy carbon electrode was prepared and successfully utilized for AA electrocatalysis. For the first time in literature, we reported the oxidation of AA at a very low potential, i.e. -140 mV vs Ag/AgCl with the detection limit upto 150 nM in pH 7 PBS. Interference studies revealed high selectivity of the present system. AA containing pharmaceutical formulations was successfully demonstrated.

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